

A Narrative Review on Menstrual Disorders and Adolescent's Health-Related Quality of Life: Implications for Midwifery Practice

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Abstract

Globally, menstrual disorders are significant health concern affecting a substantial proportion of adolescent girls, profoundly impacting their Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL). These conditions frequently cause physical discomfort, emotional distress, and social challenges, necessitating supportive care and management. This review aimed to synthesize evidence on the multifaceted quality-of-life impacts of menstrual disorders on adolescents and derive implications for midwifery practice. The data for this review paper were gathered from published studies utilizing electronic databases of Medline, Science direct, PubMed, and Google Scholar which were searched using the keywords: menstrual disorders, adolescents HRQoL, impact of menstrual disorders on adolescents HRQoL and midwifery practice. The Biopsychosocial Model was used as the foundational basis to understand the holistic impact of menstrual disorders. The date limit considered in the literature search was from 2012 - 2024 to capture the variables identified in the review. The study revealed that adolescent with dysmenorrhea, heavy menstrual bleeding, and other menstrual disorders experience substantial deficits across physical, psychological, social, academic, and other quality-of-life domains. Furthermore, severe pain, fatigue, school absenteeism, anxiety and depression were common impacts reported. It also established midwives plays a vital role in supporting adolescents with menstrual disorders to provide comprehensive education, counseling, and management strategies to acquire an optimal health-related quality of life (HRQoL). Menstrual disorders profoundly affect adolescents who are vulnerable population at the transitional stage of life. This makes it important for midwives who are the frontline of pivotal care to contribute to adolescents overall well-being and HRQoL while preventing long-lasting complications.

Keywords: Adolescents, Health-related Quality of Life (HRQoL), Menstrual Disorders, Midwifery, Midwifery Practice

1. Introduction

Menstrual disorders refer to any abnormal or irregular patterns in menstrual flow, often causing physical discomfort, emotional distress, and disruption in daily activities. They are a significant health concern affecting a substantial proportion of adolescent girls' worldwide (Laksham *et al.*, 2019). These disorders encompass a range of conditions that can profoundly impact the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of adolescents (Knox *et al.*, 2015). Menstrual disorders are one of the most occurring gynecological issues affecting women of child bearing age with a global prevalence of 75% which are the main reason for gynaecology visits (Odongo *et al.*, 2023). World Health Organization WHO (2019) refers to adolescence as a critical transitional period of growth and development spanning the ages of 10 to 19 years. Adolescent HRQoL is a multidimensional concept that reflects the physical, mental, and social well-being in relations to their overall health status (Braithwaite *et al.*, 2020).

There are 1.3 billion adolescents globally making up a total of 16% of the world's population (UNICEF Data, 2024). The population of adolescents represents 23% of the 1.1 billion people living in sub-Saharan Africa with over 30 million living in Nigeria and about a half of them are girls between the ages of 10-19 (Kumbeni, 2021). This period is particularly vulnerable to the adverse effects of menstrual disorders as it is characterized by the onset of menarche, an important biological milestone which marks the initiation of reproductive capability (Singh *et al.*, 2019). Menstrual disorders during this period can disrupt normal development and transcend to long-lasting implications beyond adolescence as shown by a study that dysmenorrhea in adolescence is a risk factor for chronic pelvic pain in adulthood (Knox *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, heavy menstrual bleeding is said to be an indication of endometrial hyperplasia and the risk of endometrial cancer in later life (Hapangama and Bulmer, 2016).

The prevalence and multidimensional impact of menstrual disorders on adolescents' HRQoL highlight the critical need for effective interventions to address this issue. Addressing these disorders is crucial not only for improving the

immediate HRQoL of adolescents but also for preventing potential long-term adverse effects on their health and well-being. Despite the high prevalence and significant impact on HRQoL, menstrual disorders among adolescents often remain under-diagnosed and undertreated (Borzutzky and Jaffray, 2020). Many adolescents perceive menstrual disorders as a normal part of menstrual cycle which are often dismissed as mere inconveniences and do not seek medical attention, while others may face barriers such as stigma, lack of education or limited access to healthcare services (Chaudhuri and Adhikary, 2021). This lack of treatment for menstrual disorders among adolescents poses a significant challenge that requires attention from healthcare providers, including midwives, to improve the overall health and well-being of this vulnerable population.

Midwives play a vital role in addressing menstrual disorders and promoting adolescent health. As primary healthcare providers, midwives are uniquely positioned to provide comprehensive care, including education, counselling and management of menstrual disorders (Phillippi and Barger, 2015). This makes midwives ideally positioned to address this immense public health issue through patient education, self-care support, assessment and management of disorder severity, and advocacy efforts to promote menstrual health and empower adolescents experiencing menstrual disorders (Gouse *et al.*, 2021). However, many midwives report feeling inadequately prepared to address menstrual disorders, citing a lack of specific training and resources (Plesons *et al.*, 2021). Hence this review aims to discuss the adolescent HRQoL and implications for midwifery practice

2. Menstrual Disorders and Adolescent Health-Related Quality of Life

Adolescence is a crucial time for establishing healthy menstrual patterns. Unfortunately, menstrual disorders are quite common during this period, impacting a young woman's health-related quality of life (HRQoL) across physical, emotional, social, academic, and other domains during this critical developmental period (Laksham *et al.*, 2019). It ranges from dysmenorrhea (painful menstruation), menorrhagia (heavy menstrual

bleeding), amenorrhea (absence of menstruation), and irregular menstrual cycles and they are individual-specific (Ojoade and Adesegha, 2021; Knox *et al.*, 2015). Some of the symptoms peculiar to menstrual disorders are abdominal pain was the major contributor followed by backache, irritability, weakness, psychological stress, generalized body pains, headache, dizziness and nausea and vomiting (Shoor, 2017). Initially, the menstrual cycle may be irregular, with longer or shorter intervals between periods. This irregularity is generally due to hormonal fluctuations as the body adjusts to the rhythm of menstruation. It often takes around two years for the menstrual cycle to stabilize into a consistent pattern (Sobczyńska-Malefora and Bergeant, 2020).

Dysmenorrhea, the aforementioned painful periods is the most common gynecologic complaint among adolescent presenting with painful menstrual cramps that occur shortly before or during menstruation (Amu and Bamidele, 2021). It can range from mild discomfort to severe pain, often accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea. Primary dysmenorrhea is the most common type and occurs without any underlying medical condition while secondary dysmenorrhea is caused by an underlying medical condition, such as endometriosis or uterine fibroids (Sanfilippo *et al.*, 2021). Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) is cyclic constellation of symptoms occurring in second half of menstrual cycle, the symptoms occur a week to 10 days between the start of menstrual blood loss. It has been estimated that the frequency of PMS is high and the symptoms include bloating, weight gain, myalgia, backache, headache, tiredness, lethargy, fatigue, breast tenderness, depressive mood, irritability and decrease in concentration (Rajipet *et al.*, 2021). Amenorrhea is the absence of menstruation for three or more menstrual cycles (Chhabra, 2021) presenting with total cessation of menses. Amenorrhea can be caused by factors such as excessive exercise, low body weight, primary hypogonadism, pituitary or other endocrine gland disorders, hormonal imbalances, or polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) (Odongo *et al.*, 2023; Chhabra, 2021).

Menorrhagia is characterized by prolonged or excessively heavy menstrual bleeding and adolescent girls experiencing menorrhagia may

find their periods lasting longer than seven days or requiring the use of multiple sanitary products within a short period. Several factors can contribute to menorrhagia, including hormonal imbalances, uterine fibroids, hormonal contraceptives, or bleeding disorders. The term oligomenorrhea (from the Greek word oligos meaning few) refers to menstrual cycles longer than 35 days and less than 90 days (Ye *et al.*, 2020). Most cases of oligomenorrhea occur in the first decade after menarche and the most common cause is poly- cystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS). Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a hormonal disorder characterized by increased androgen levels, irregular menstrual cycles, and cysts in the ovaries (Braumah *et al.*, 2020). Adolescent girls with PCOS may experience infrequent or prolonged menstrual periods, excessive hair growth, acne, and weight gain. PCOS is also associated with insulin resistance and can increase the risk of long-term health issues such as diabetes and cardiovascular disease (Ho *et al.*, 2021).

An individual's health is visualized from two major perspectives, the physical wellbeing and the mental health. HRQoL is the culmination of these two facets of life as the state of the physical well-being can translate to psychological well-being (Karimi and Brazier, 2016). The Health-Related Quality of Life of a person covers a wide range, including psychological, social, physical and environmental factors and wellbeing. These physiological abnormalities cause adverse effect to body system, including severe bleeding, abnormal bleeding, and other associative symptoms, thereby resulting in physical and emotional harm (Knox *et al.*, 2019) in tandem their Health-related quality of life (HRQoL) when not addressed early. Adolescent go through several hormonal changes which can change their menstrual pattern (Shin *et al.*, 2022). These menstrual disorders are confused with menstrual pattern and in some cases, adolescents are unaware that their menstrual patterns are abnormal and can lead to long-term consequences (Odongo *et al.*, 2023). Past research suggests social support, sleep quality and depression are interrelated with menstrual health and HRQoL in adolescents (Gomes *et al.* 2020) which is also reported by Zhan *et al.* (2020) that sleep quality and depressive feelings are predictors of HRQoL

Several consequences can result from menstrual disorders relatively transcending to reduced HRQoL the disease burden attributed to the disorder include dizziness, headache, depression, and anxiety (Adebimpe *et al.*, 2016). It is a common cause of school absenteeism resulting in poor academic performance (Shin *et al.*, 2022) and significantly add to problems during the growth and development phase. This speaks to the fact that all the problems adolescent girls face and result into a reduced HRQoL resulting into long-lasting complications both at the reproductive and psychological phase.

2.1 Prevalent Menstrual Disorders and its Impact on Adolescent Girls

Menstrual disorders are not uncommon companions on a young woman's journey into womanhood. Several menstrual disorders exists ranging from dysmenorrhea (painful menstruation), menorrhagia (heavy menstrual bleeding), amenorrhea (absence of menstruation), to irregular menstrual cycles (Ojoade and Adesegha, 2021; Knox *et al.*, 2015), however not all menstrual disorders are prevalent as evidenced by studies estimating that up to 90% and 75.3% of adolescent girls experience dysmenorrhea (Goss, 2023; Kareem *et al.*, 2020) while Borzutzky and Jaffray (2020) established that menorrhagia affects approximately 37% of adolescents. Furthermore, a study in Lebanese on the prevalence of menstrual disorders showed irregular menstrual cycles (80.7%), premenstrual syndrome (54%), dysmenorrhea (38.1%), polymenorrhea (37.5%) and Oligomenorrhea (19.3%) (Karout *et al.*, 2012). Dysmenorrhea is said to be the most common menstrual disorder and irregular menstrual cycles, which can be a sign of underlying endocrine disorders, are also common during adolescence, affecting up to 20% of girls in this age group (Rajiwade *et al.*, 2017).

The vibrant colors of a healthy HRQoL such as physical well-being, emotional stability, and a flourishing social life can be dulled by the presence of menstrual disorders. Prolonged menstrual disorders can cause significant damage to the body especially the reproductive system in relations to physical components and psychological problems. The emotional toll can be just as significant, with

anxiety and even depression sometimes accompanying the physical discomfort such as stress which can in-turn be associated with depression as evidenced by Kahal *et al.* (2023), dysmenorrhea and menorrhagia can also be associated with increased levels of anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem (Sachedina and Todd 2020; Bajalan *et al.*, 2018). The physical manifestations, like pain and fatigue, can lead to school absenteeism and difficulty participating in activities of daily living.

The social implications of menstrual disorders are also significant including fear of leaks and the limitations imposed by heavy bleeding or debilitating cramps can lead to social isolation and reluctance to participate in activities that were once a source of joy (Hennegan *et al.*, 2019; Miirio *et al.*, 2018). Menstrual disorders can also affect adolescents' participation in extracurricular activities, sports, and social events, further limiting their social interactions and potentially leading to feelings of exclusion and loneliness (Johnston *et al.*, 2020) which can negatively impact their interpersonal relationships and overall social functioning. These prevalent menstrual disorders in adolescent girls can take a lot of toll on their wellbeing and which makes early detection and diagnosis viable to mitigate the condition.

Figure 1: Biopsychosocial Model (Gliedt *et al.*, 2017)

The Biopsychosocial Model (BPS) model provides a valuable framework for understanding menstrual disorders in adolescents by emphasizing the need

to consider the dimensions. Biological factors include the underlying pathophysiology that directly cause symptoms like pelvic pain and nausea. However, the model highlights that biological factors interact bi-directionally with psychological aspects including mood disorders, low self-esteem, and maladaptive thought patterns that can heighten pain sensitivity and exacerbate disability (Gagnon *et al.*, 2022). Social elements such as menstrual stigma, gender inequities, and socioeconomic barriers to care-seeking also play a role in the adolescent's experience of menstrual disorder impacts. This BPS assessment model would allow midwives to uncover the diverse factors that contribute to menstrual disorder impacts on the quality of life, then target biological aspects through evidence-based pain relief approaches while also addressing unmet psychosocial needs through education, counselling, cognitive-behavioural techniques and advocacy to promote a supportive school and family environment (Eri *et al.*, 2020).

3. Implications for Midwifery Practice

The evidence on the impacts of menstrual disorders on adolescent HRQoL has profound implications for guiding efforts across midwifery practice. Midwifery looks to cushion the effect of menstrual disorders on adolescent girls and give a better end product to the already stated after effect of menstrual disorders. Midwives can be seen as contributors to the general health and welfare of adolescent girls, in helping them manage and address their menstrual disorder to avoid reproductive and long-lasting implications.

The findings of this study necessitate generating a well-reasoned educative regime and awareness programmes that not only addresses the ignorance and its consequences in adolescent girls, but also empowers them with information on health habits and identifying menstrual patterns. Midwives can be agents of counselling and support to adolescent girls suffering from menstrual disorders as they are most times prone to isolation, shame and self-esteem decline. Expert guidelines emphasize midwives should routinely screen for menstrual disorders, assess their multidimensional impacts using validated measures, and educate adolescents on self-care strategies. At organizational and policy

levels, midwives should advocate for improved school accommodations, youth-friendly reproductive health services, and access to care for adolescents with menstrual disorders. In summary, fully realizing these key implications for comprehensively advancing midwifery practice will enable the profession to have an enormously positive impact on the lives of adolescents suffering from undertreated menstrual disorders worldwide.

4. Conclusion

Adolescents around the globe suffer profound sequelae from inadequately managed menstrual disorders. Addressing menstrual disorders is paramount due to their significant impact on health-related quality of life (HRQoL) but despite their prevalence, menstrual disorders often go under-diagnosed and under-treated. Midwives, as primary healthcare providers, play a pivotal role in supporting adolescents with menstrual disorders to provide comprehensive education, counseling, and management strategies for adolescent girls. However, immense unmet needs and barriers are preventing vulnerable youth from achieving an acceptable quality of life. By prioritizing adolescent menstrual health and empowering midwives with the required tools, the outcome of their menstrual health can be significantly improved therefore leaving a way for healthier reproductive life.

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